

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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California State University, Long Beach
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PROGRAM EVALUATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF A NURSE EDUCATION
MODULE TO IMPROVE PSYCHIATRIC PATIENT AGITATION/ANXIETY
ASSESSMENT AND CARE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Admission to a psychiatric inpatient unit can be a stressful experience and often times patients are admitted in a state of crisis. This state of crisis can elicit emotions of agitation and/or anxiety. When these emotions are not quickly addressed there is an increased safety risk for psychiatric staff caring for these patients. This DNP project provides a programmatic evaluation that includes a review of the literature. The review of literature was used in the development of targeted nursing education designed to address anxiety and agitation on an inpatient adult psychiatric unit. A care protocol was then developed. This protocol would allow nurses to administer oral as needed (PRN) medications (ordered by the psychiatric physicians upon admission) to patients that met criteria. This project proposes that programmatic evaluation resulting in targeted nursing education can result in earlier assessment of anxiety and agitation in the psychiatric patient. An early assessment should lead to faster administration of oral psychotropics and potentially avoid negative sequelae such as incidents of assault against staff members (workplace violence), code grey alarms, seclusion and restraints.

Keywords: psychiatry, nurse education module, PRN medications, workplace violence, program evaluation

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BACKGROUND

The hospital inpatient psychiatric unit is an environment created for individuals who are in an active state of crisis. There is an expectation that this environment should be safe for both patients and staff members. Safety may be difficult to maintain when newly admitted patients or those with acutely worsening conditions are placed in a locked psychiatric unit with limited freedom. Often the stressors that can potentially trigger patients and lead to increased agitation include: being held involuntarily on a legally binding hold, having certain belongings removed from their possession, being restricted to specific hours of visitation with loved ones, and interacting with similarly stressed patients. While this list is not exhaustive, it gives a glimpse into the external factors that patients can experience on the inpatient psychiatric unit. As a result, both the newly admitted patient or a patient that has otherwise been stable on the unit can begin to escalate and externalize aggressive behaviors which have the potential to result in unsafe situations up to and including an act of violence towards staff members.

Pertinent issues to consider in relation to patient agitation involve internal factors unique to each individual. These internal factors include a mental health crisis and disease process. The National Alliance on Mental Illness defines a mental health crisis as, “..any situation in which a person’s behavior puts them at risk of hurting themselves or others and/or prevents them from being able to care for themselves or function effectively in the community” (2018). Mental health crises therefore have the potential to result in the violent acts such as verbal, physical or sexual abuse. Since it is impossible to predict the actions that an individual will commit as a patient it is important that healthcare workers observe closely for subtle changes in behavior and/or mood during an initial

escalation period. These signs may be manifested through actions, behaviors, or verbal statements made by the patient indicating increasing levels of frustration.

The disease process of each individual is unique in that symptomatology varies. While the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual, Fifth Edition (DSM-5) has objective and subjective criteria for each mental health diagnosis, there are variations in the symptoms that each patient may display within their disease process (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Disease processes associated with aggressive behavior according to the DSM-5 are summarized in (Appendix C).

While the summary is not to be viewed as an exhaustive list of the DSM V disorders, it depicts the most frequent psychiatric disorders within the adult population according to the National Alliance on Mental Illness (2019). The relevancy of this table is even better understood when one considers the large academic medical center located in Southern California, where this quality improvement project will be conducted, does not have a substance abuse withdrawal treatment program therefore substance intoxication and withdrawal disorder diagnoses are not included within the patient population of this evidence-based quality improvement project. Additionally, adolescent patients will be excluded in the proposed project thus disorders (ie. disruptive and neurodevelopmental disorders) commonly diagnosed within the pediatric / adolescent population likely will not apply to the patients within this project.

In conclusion, it is important that the healthcare provider observes closely for any early escalation periods in order to effectively initiate early interventions such as therapeutic communication, as needed or “PRN” medications, and various other individualized therapies. As needed (PRN) medications vary in pharmacological category

according to the diagnosis of the patient. Psychiatric PRN medications are typically utilized to address acute psychosis, agitation, or anxiety. This evidence-based quality improvement project will focus on: 1) a systematic review of the literature related to care and practices that facilitate a safe environment of care on a psychiatric unit, 2) development of a nursing education module related to optimal nursing assessment / care practices, and 3) the development of a protocol that includes psychiatric PRN medications and assessment techniques designed to de-escalate a patient in the inpatient psychiatric nursing unit before an act of violence is made by the patient towards themselves or a healthcare provider.

Significance

In 2018 the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) reported an increase of 72% in workplace violence rates between 2012 to 2015. The NIOSH also reported a rise in injuries for full time employees from 4.4 to 7.2 (injuries per 1,000 employees) in the same period (2018). In 2016 the Bureau of Labor Statistics reported that 16, 890 workers experienced “nonfatal workplace violence” in private industries. The Bureau of Labor Statistics also reported that 70% of these victims were female and worked in either healthcare or the social assistance industry (2016).

A large academic medical center in Southern California currently utilizes multiple workplace violence prevention interventions. These interventions include: police and security officer assistance as needed, a “code grey” alarm system to be used when there is a perceived threat or concern for safety, a show of support by staff members within neighboring psychiatric units (“silent code”), required annual Nonviolent Crisis Intervention Training (CPI) by every staff member in psychiatry, electronic incident

reporting system, and administrative investigation/follow-up of violent events. These interventions are by no means an exhaustive list, however they depict the most commonly utilized violence prevention mechanisms at this large academic medical center in Southern California.

Incidents of aggression have the potential to impact healthcare workers physical, emotional, and interpersonal well-being. These adverse effects will then carry over to the work environment potentially causing staff burnout and decreased job satisfaction. Improving the environment of safety on the inpatient psychiatric unit can aid in decreasing violent events carried out by patients against healthcare workers. The large academic medical center in Southern California previously described has already implemented several of these prevention interventions.

Decreasing violence on the inpatient unit through early implementation of a set of evidence-based nursing interventions has the potential to improve nurses' perception of empowerment. A change in nurses' perception of empowerment could serve as a preventive measure to reduce violent events in the future. Finally, staff may be less likely to develop burnout or decreased job satisfaction if they are given effective tools to de-escalate patients. The review of literature will further expand on the significance of the aforementioned associations as shown in recent literature.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this DNP project was to conduct a two phase quality improvement project using a programmatic review approach along with a review of the literature to develop a nurse education module in order to improve patient agitation and/or anxiety

assessment and PRN medication protocol for use by psychiatric nursing staff in order to enhance milieu safety at a large academic medical center in Southern California.

Problem Objectives

The objectives of this evidence-based quality improvement project included: 1) the development of a nurse education module aimed at teaching psychiatric nurses to measure anxiety and agitation in psychiatric patients 2) ensuring that psychiatric residents evaluated newly admitted psychiatric patients for appropriate medication management options which would enable staff members to proactively treat acute changes in behavior / thought processes 3) reviewing the effectiveness of the psychiatric medication protocol by comparing pre-protocol and post-protocol implementation incident report rates of verbal / physical / sexual abuse, quantity of violence in progress “code grey” alarms, and occurrence of restrictive measures (seclusion/restraints) and lastly 4) evaluating the medication protocols effect on nursing staff member’s perception of empowerment.

Definition of Terms

Verbal abuse - For the purpose of this quality improvement project verbal abuse will refer to OSHA’s definition of “verbal violence”. OSHA defines this as, “...threats, verbal abuse, hostility, harassment and the like – which can cause significant psychological trauma and stress, even if no physical injury takes place” (Occupational Safety and Health Administration, 2015).

Physical abuse – For the purpose of this quality improvement project physical abuse will refer to any physical acts of violence inflicted upon a staff member by a patient (may or may not result in injury). Physical abuse on a staff member may or may not result in

charges of assault/battery against the perpetrator by the Police Department at the academic medical center.

Sexual abuse - For the purpose of this quality improvement project sexual abuse will refer to any sexual contact made by patients towards staff members. Sexual abuse may result in charges against the perpetrator for sexual assault by the Police Department at the academic medical center.

Code grey alarm - defined by academic medical center as an alarm intended to, “..summon security assistance and should be activated when there is a real or perceived threat of immediate danger such as a violent/combative patient, visitor or staff member” (2018)

Seclusion - Locked seclusion room that prohibits patient from leaving their locked quarters while they are agitated. Does not restrict extremity range of motion. To be discontinued if patient begins to exhibit a reduction in agitation. If no reduction in agitation then renewal order must be placed.

Restraints - Walking restraints, 4-point restraints, or 5-point restraints

Iowa Model Revised as Framework

The Iowa model of evidence-based practice revised to promote quality of care is a tool developed to lead practice driven changes with an emphasis on utilizing evidence-based research. The Iowa model is often used to guide implementation of evidence-based practice and provides an algorithm to direct actions in order to effectively achieve a process improvement goal. The Iowa model consists of a seven-step process for change (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). The first step is to identify a problem-focused trigger that could be utilized as an opportunity for improvement. In this DNP project, the trigger

for the problem of violence in the psychiatric healthcare setting. In the Iowa model, the second step is a statement of the problem. In this DNP project, the identified need for change is in the incident rates related to verbal / physical / sexual abuse, code gray alarms, and use of restrictive measures (seclusion / restraints). The Iowa model offers three decision point opportunities to help direct the quality improvement project. The first decision point is to decide if the presented topic is a priority for the organization. The large academic medical center in Southern California which was used as the inpatient psychiatric facility for this project, has an interest in reducing violent events within the psychiatric healthcare center in 2020. They are dedicated to promoting a safe environment at all times for their caregivers.

The next step in the Iowa model is to form a team. The DNP candidate will collaborate with the director of psychiatry, the attending physicians of the adult units, the AM/PM/NOC nurses assigned to the adult units, and the psychiatric residents / fellows. Literature must be reviewed, evaluated, and synthesized in step four of the Iowa model. This is also the second decision point. Once the evidence shows sufficient support for change then the project can be designed.

Step five of the Iowa model is to develop a standard of EBP and a plan to execute the change. The focus of developing a standardized process is to examine best practices that demonstrate how to effectively achieve earlier de-escalation of crisis situations and ongoing management in order to decrease the potential risk for violence events in this healthcare setting. The guidelines will require psychiatric physician residents to assess each newly admitted patient, and obtain a signature for the corresponding consent form related to the PRN oral medication. The oral medications included in this protocol are

Risperidone, Zyprexa, Haldol and Ativan. The psychiatric nurses will then use the PANSS-EC and CUXOS tool as indicated for any acute changes in behavior related to agitation / anxiety.

Lastly, once the project is completed then the data will be collected and reviewed. Results will be distributed to administrative personnel to discuss the potential for continued implementation and incorporation of changes into practice. If any adaptations or changes are needed for continued implementation this will be discussed as well in order to ensure that the change can be successfully sustained within the organization.

The focus of this quality improvement DNP project is to develop a nurse education module that will instruct nurses on early de-escalation of agitation/anxiety through a PRN oral medication as ordered by psychiatric residents which will aid in reducing the risk of violence that is inherently present on a psychiatric unit (see figure 1 below).

Figure 1 Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017

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REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The aim of this DNP project was to assess stakeholder concerns through a programmatic review that would address a gap in psychiatric care processes resulting in violence within the healthcare setting. The literature was evaluated for evidence-based practices that could be incorporated into a toolkit. The toolkit requires implementation of a nurse education module in order to aid in the early assessment of psychiatric patient agitation/anxiety resulting in crisis prevention intervention. A comprehensive literature review was conducted related to violence in the healthcare setting, psychotropic medications (antipsychotic and anxiolytics) and assessment tools utilized for acute agitation and anxiety. The following research databases were examined: OneSearch, PsycINFO, PsychARTICLES, CINAHL, PubMed, and Google Scholar. Additionally, key articles found within the above databases were reviewed for relevant references that provided further supportive research. See Table 1 below for further description of the literature search.

Table 1

Index of Health Literature Search

Topic	Search Term	Search Term Combination	Articles Found	Titles Reviewed	Abstracts Reviewed	Articles Used
Violence in healthcare	Violence in healthcare	Violence in healthcare	68,508	200	25	2
	Violence against nurses	Violence against nurses	30,213	100	10	2
	Impact of violence in healthcare	Impact of violence against nurses	16,624	100	20	5
Psychotropic medications	Antipsychotics	Effective oral antipsychotic	12,055	150	15	2

		Atypical antipsychotic and agitation	2, 154	100	3	0
	Anxiolytics	Effective oral anxiolytic	4, 310	100	4	0
	As needed psychiatric medications	PRN psychiatric medication	1,992	100	12	3
Agitation and anxiety rating scales	Assessment scale of anxiety and agitation	Anxiety and agitation rating scale	6, 093	200	20	1
		Overt Agitation Severity Scale	701	50	10	1
		Assessment and management of agitation	4, 085	100	10	3

Note. Articles were excluded based on article relevance, non-English language or published before 2010, unless the article or study was noted to be the seminal work related to the topic.

Violence in the Healthcare Setting

Violence rates have been increasing in healthcare settings across the United States. California Senate Bill 1299 was approved by Governor Brown in 2014 and imposes stricter regulations for hospitals related to workplace violence prevention (California Legislative Information). This bill places the responsibility of workplace violence prevention on the employers and employees. It requires a system for reporting and tracking violent events, a program to prevent violent events, and collaboration with law enforcement officials when violence occurs. There are many more requirements under Senate Bill 1299 (2014) however these are the most imperative requirements found within the bill. Hospitals are expected to have a written prevention plan and log of violent incidents starting on April 2017. As of April 2018, hospitals are required to have a formal

workplace violence prevention plan implemented as well as workplace violence prevention training (Gooch, 2018). Senate Bill 1299 applies to: “..general acute care hospital or an acute psychiatric hospital” (California Legislative Information, 2013-2014). The bill also requires Occupational Safety and Health Administration to develop standardized recommendations related to workplace violence. These recommendations will be further discussed as they pertain to workplace violence prevention plans.

The rates of violence in the California healthcare facilities enrolled in the violence reporting system set in place from Senate Bill 1299 were released for 2017 and 2018. The rates for 2017 (July 1st to September 30th) revealed 2,177 incidents for the 257 hospitals enrolled during that time period (Sum, 2018). There was no summary of unit locations provided for this report. The rates for 2018 (October 1, 2017 to September 30th 2018) disclosed 9, 436 incidents of violence for the 365 hospitals enrolled during that time period (California Division of Occupational Safety and Health, 2019). From these reported incidents 16% occurred on a behavioral health unit (California Division of Occupational Safety and Health, 2019).

Due to the increasing prevalence, the focus of violence prevention has recently shifted from the state level to a national level. This includes efforts to create a national minimum standard of safety for all eligible hospitals in relation to preventing violence in the healthcare environment including psychiatric units. In 2018, Representative Ro Khanna proposed such a bill directed at garnering support from the Secretary of Labor which resulted in the proposition of H.R. 5223 (2018). The bill sought adoption of Occupational and Safety Health standards by the Secretary of Labor for all applicable health care facilities. Soon after the bill died in congress, Representative Joe Courtney

continued to advocate on the importance of addressing violence in the healthcare setting by introducing a new bill H.R. 1309 in 2019. Representative Joe Courtney included “any psychiatric treatment facility” as one of the targets of his proposed legislation (H.R. 1309, 2019). This bill is supported by Representative Ro Khanna, the American Psychiatric Nurses Association, and several other prominent support groups / individuals (Press Release, 2019). These recent legislative initiatives continue to emphasize the importance of addressing violence in the health care workplace setting which includes psychiatric units.

Recommendations for Violence Prevention

In 2016, The Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) released guidelines aimed at reducing workplace violence. The OSHA guidelines list psychiatric facilities as one of their proposed target populations. The recommendations by OSHA for workplace violence prevention are the standards proposed for adoption by congressional representatives in the previously mentioned bills. The Occupational Safety and Health Administration organization describes a successful violence prevention program as including: “...management commitment and employee participation, worksite analysis, hazard prevention and control, safety and health training, and lastly recordkeeping and program evaluation” (p. 5, 2016). “Management commitment” refers to the commitment related to the adoption of appropriate violence prevention measures, proper education of staff members and establishment of appropriate policies and procedures related to violence prevention. “Worksite analysis” includes hazard assessment through logs and feedback (management, employee or patient), and analysis of reported events. “Hazard prevention and control” refers to the identification of workplace environmental or safety

risks, development of interventions to reduce these hazards, and the evaluation of these interventions for effectiveness (Occupational Health and Safety Administration, 2016).

The fourth key to a successful violence prevention program is “safety and health training” and is the most relevant to this project. It refers to staff education and training related to workplace violence prevention. The final step in the prevention program is the “recordkeeping and program evaluation” which consists of maintaining a log related to incidents of workplace violence and reviewing these logs for potential improvements within the facility (Occupational Health and Safety Administration [OSHA], 2016).

Staff safety and health training as defined by OSHA will be an important focus within this project. The safety training will include training on early detection of “escalating behaviors” that present a threat to safety and training on techniques to de-escalate these behaviors such as administration of medications (Occupational Health and Safety Administration, 2016). This evidence-based programmatic review project resulted in the construction of a nurse education module for an inpatient psychiatric unit in an effort to decrease the risk of violent events towards healthcare workers. The module is consistent with the OSHA guidelines for healthcare that were released in 2016.

Effects of Violence on Healthcare Workers

The effects of violence in the healthcare setting are likely to differ with each individual based on the severity of the assault, the coping mechanisms of the individual and their past experiences with violence. In 2008, The Department of Health and Human Services, The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention and the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health collaborated to release the effects of exposure to stress on healthcare workers. One of the factors linked to stress was an “...exposure to work-

related violence or threats” (HHS, CDC, & NIOSH, 2008). The effects can include psychological changes, somatic complaints and behavioral disruptions for each individual. This may include: “...irritability, job dissatisfaction, depression, sleep problems, absenteeism, headache, upset stomach, changes in blood pressure, and post-traumatic stress disorder” (HHS, CDC, & NIOSH, p.3, 2008). The studies conducted to review the effects of violence on nurses in the healthcare field will be reviewed as follows. Further information on these studies is included in Appendix A.

The effect of violence was studied on a population of twenty-two Iranian nurses with workplace violence experience in a qualitative study. Interviews were conducted to evaluate their perceptions of impact (Najafi, Fallahi-Khoshknab, Ahmadi, Dalvandi, Rahgozar, 2017). The thematic elements uncovered were consequences of “individual-familial” and “destructive career” (Najafi et al., 2017). The individual-familial consequences included “negative feelings”, “reduced tolerance” and “destruction of family relationships” (Najafi et al., p. 119, 2017). Subsequently the destructive career effects included: “undesirable care consequences”, “negative attitude towards the nursing profession”, “feelings of fear and insecurity in the workplace”, “the contagious nature of violence”, “destruction of professional confidence”, “poor communication”, and “retaliatory behavior” (Najafi et al., p. 119, 2017).

In a second study the impact of violence was studied in relation to quality of life in 387 nurses within psychiatric hospitals located in northern and southern China (Zeng et al., 2013). This cross sectional, quantitative study utilized “The Medical Outcome Study 36-Item Short Form” to assess eight health categories of physical, mental and emotional health (Zeng et al., 2013). Upon its completion the researchers learned that the

psychiatric nurses with workplace violence experience had a decreased score in quality of life related to the physical and mental categories of the survey when compared to their colleagues who had no experiences (Zeng et al., 2013).

These two studies demonstrate the increased risk of adverse effects that nurses face regarding violence in the healthcare setting. The study conducted in Iran showed the interpersonal effects of violence whereas the study conducted in China demonstrated the direct impact on nurses' well-being. Both studies demonstrate the negative effects of violence in the healthcare setting. This unfortunate impact on the lives of caregivers across the world is a deserving of increased efforts to enhance workplace safety. Caregivers should never be afraid to go to work and perform their duties.

In 2018, a cross-sectional quantitative study on mental health nurses was published. This study further reviewed the effects of violence on nurses in China. The study was located Wuhan, China. The anonymous surveys resulted in 245 completed surveys for a response rate of 84.5% (Yang, Stone, Petrini, & Morris, 2018). The nurses answered questions related to workplace violence and the Maslach Burnout Inventory-General Survey. The purpose of the survey was to uncover the effects of violence on mental health nurses. The results of the study showed that 94.6% of nurses had experienced workplace violence (Yang et al., 2018). A few of the primary effects related to workplace violence include: "feelings of injustice, depression or anger" for 61.3% of nurses, "reduced enthusiasm for work" in 34.9%, "feelings of anxiety, insomnia or fear" in 22.1%, and a "desire to leave the nursing profession" in 20% (Yang et al., p. 33, 2018).

The level of evidence for these two studies related to nurses in China is the weakest level when evaluating for the strength and rigor of scientific evidence. The

observational studies fall under the category of correlational studies (Grove, Gray & Burns, 2015). However, this does not detract from their importance in understanding the subjective effects of violence. The methodology of these studies was appropriate and they provide meaningful information to understanding the long-term consequences of the problem. This information would not have been possible through an experimental approach due to the unethical risks for participants.

This last article was a systematic literature review on the consequences of workplace violence. The review contained 68 total articles which included quantitative studies and quality improvement reports. From the 68 articles reviewed, 16 of the articles included were based in the United States. The articles were described as cross-sectional surveys, prospective cohort studies, or administrative data. Descriptive statistics were utilized to analyze the studies. Results were divided among the following categories: physical, psychological, emotional, work function, patient relationship / quality of care, social or general, and lastly financial effects (Lanctot & Guay, 2014). There were 29 studies that found individuals to have physical effects after experiencing aggression related to workplace violence. The various physical complaints found within the studies included headaches, stomach aches, and pain (Lanctot & Guay, 2014). Psychological effects were reported in 47 studies. The effects included: symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder, depression, emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, burnout, anxiety, lack of self-esteem and negative mental health (Lanctot & Guay, 2014).

The emotional effects of workplace violence were reported in 25 articles. The emotional effects and included: anger, guilt, powerlessness, fear, surprise, humiliation, sadness, and vulnerability (Lanctot & Guay, 2014). Work function effects were reported

in 70.6% of the studies. The effects found within various studies included: wanting to quit one's job, going on sick leave, transferring to another job, negative effect on performance, and reduction in organizational commitment (Lanctot & Guay, 2014). Patient relationship and quality of care consequences were found in 10 studies. The effects were fear towards patients by staff, reduced quality of care, a reduction in pleasure performing work, and reduced time spent with patients (Lanctot & Guay, 2014). The social and general effects of workplace violence were noted in just four studies. These effects included an effect of violence on their lives outside of the work place, and a disruption in social, relational and familial life (Lanctot & Guay, 2014). Lastly, financial effects related to workplace violence were only discussed in four of the articles reviewed. The fiscal results of workplace violence varies vastly according to each setting and study. It is of note however what these financial losses are related to within the overall schema. The losses reported were commonly the result of employee absences due to workplace injuries sustained as a direct result of violence (Lanctot & Guay, 2014).

The limitation, presented from the studies performed in Iran and China, is found in the generalizability across various countries. Each country holds unique traditions and has its own structure within their healthcare setting. It may be difficult to generalize certain components of these studies (ie. incidence rates or types of violence) when reviewing workplace violence effect however it should be noted that the overall effect of violence is the main concept of interest. The subjective feelings of these nurses are the primary focus and that is why these studies were included within this review of workplace violence effects.

The victimization of nurses within various healthcare settings will be exacerbated if nothing is done to stop the vicious cycle of workplace violence. Violence rates in the healthcare setting have increased over the years and research has been shown to support the negative effects over time from these incidents on the overall well-being of nurses. The negative effects of violence are so vast it is apparent that more interventions are needed to continue in the prevention efforts to combat this epidemic within the healthcare field.

National guidelines have included several tiers of recommendations related to violence prevention within the workplace. The environment in which this project will be carried out currently has a workplace violence prevention program in place. The current components include: collaboration with on-site law enforcement and safety officers, a ‘code grey’ (violence in progress) alarm system to request additional support staff during incidents of violence, an electronic incident reporting and monitoring system, a ‘code lavender’ debriefing process for staff after stressful events, and continued administrative efforts in the evolving process of violence reduction within the workplace. Therefore, administration of oral psychotropics for acute agitation and anxiety will be the primary intervention utilized within this DNP project to enhance milieu safety.

Recommendations for Psychopharmacology and Screening Tools

The psychopharmacologic management of psychiatric disorders is one of the treatment modalities that holds the greatest significance in the stabilization process. Often it is described as an art and a science mixed together. Finding the most effective medication regimen for each individual is no easy task. What works for one individual may not be effective for another due to their genetic makeup, metabolic process or

underlying comorbidities. Therefore, this review will identify particular antipsychotics and anxiolytics found to be efficacious, safe, and rapid in reducing acute agitation and/or anxiety.

First generation antipsychotics work on the dopamine (D2) receptor sites through antagonism within the mesolimbic pathway. The proposed effect of this antagonism is a reduction in the symptoms associated with psychosis. Due to the widespread antagonism of dopamine receptor sites in not only the mesolimbic pathway but also the limbic, mesocortical and tuberoinfundibular pathways there is a potential risk of negative symptom exacerbation (Stahl, 2013). Second generation antipsychotics (also known as “atypical”) work by acting antagonistically against dopamine (D2) and serotonin (5HT2) pathways. The additional effect of serotonin blockade prevents dopamine from being released “downstream” within the striatum. In what seems like a contradiction, there are differing levels of dopamine throughout the pathways when second generation antipsychotics are taken which contributes to the reduced risk of extrapyramidal side effects and hyperprolactinemia (Stahl, 2013).

Benzodiazepines are often prescribed as the mainstream clinical treatment for acute anxiety reduction. This is typically due to their quick onset of action. Benzodiazepines are believed to act on the amygdala and prefrontal cortex through improved actions on γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA). GABA in its primary function reduces neuronal activity that is believed to be associated with anxiety (Stahl, 2013).

While it is imperative to understand the mechanism action behind antipsychotics, it is also essential to consider the onset time of action associated with each medication. The onset of action is one of the most pertinent factors to consider when selecting the

appropriate medication for the management of acute agitation. After consulting several pharmacological references such as Stahl's Prescribers Guide, Davis's Drug Guide and Mosby's Nursing Drug Reference, there was limited information regarding the onset of action related to oral antipsychotics. This is the reason intramuscular injections are typically utilized in hospitals for acute agitation/anxiety. However, for the purpose of this project, oral antipsychotics and anxiolytics will be recommended in order to aid in utilizing the least invasive treatment measures possible. Due to the reduced risk of extrapyramidal symptoms associated with second-generation antipsychotics (Stahl, 2013) the literature was searched for supportive evidence related to second-generation antipsychotic onset of action. Olanzapine oral has a peak plasma level of 3 to 6 hours (Yu et al., 2016). A few studies showed fluctuating levels of effectiveness of Olanzapine oral disintegrating tablet (ODT) after 15 to 60 minutes from variable dosages (Gault, Gray, Vilke, & Wilson, 2012).

Risperidone ODT and Risperidone oral were shown to have varying levels of efficacy in a few studies within approximately 15 to 60 minutes in varying doses as well (Gault et al., 2012). Quetiapine oral obtains a peak plasma level at approximately 90 minutes (Yu et al., 2016). Asenapine is an oral disintegrating formulation only that is not widely studied within research for the treatment of acute agitation however it should be noted that this medication may have a peak plasma level of approximately 30 to 90 minutes (Yu et al., 2016). Haloperidol is a first-generation antipsychotic that is currently still used on a routine basis as the control with which second generation antipsychotics are compared against. Haloperidol oral has an onset of approximately 30 to 60 minutes (Wilson, Pepper, Currier, Holloman, & Feifel, 2012). However, Haloperidol has higher

rates of extrapyramidal symptoms (EPS) when compared with second-generation antipsychotic agents (Yu et al., 2016).

Lorazepam oral is the most frequently studied anxiolytic agent within the benzodiazepine drug classification for the management of acute anxiety. It is frequently used in conjunction with various antipsychotic agents for the rapid reduction of acutely agitated patients. The onset of action for the oral formulation of Lorazepam is approximately 20 to 30 minutes (Wilson et al., 2012).

In 2016 an expert panel published an international consensus of recommendations related to the management of acute agitation within psychiatry using the Delphi method. The international experts that participated were from “..Argentina, Australia, Austria, Brazil, Canada, France, Germany, Greece, Hong Kong, Italy, Spain, UK and USA” (Garriga et al., 2016). The expert panel reviewed 124 research articles (39 randomized controlled trials, 30 meta-analyses, 55 observational or open label) (Garriga et al., 2016). Recommendations included management of agitation through non-pharmacological interventions as a first line approach, oral medications are preferred over intramuscular, and pharmacological interventions that are geared towards rapid efficacy (Garriga et al., 2016).

The treatment of agitation should ideally begin with a valid screening tool. The panel identified nine valid and reliable agitation screening tools. The most relevant screening tools related to this project were The Agitation Severity Scale (ASS) and The Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale Excited Component (PANSS-EC). The Agitation Severity Scale assesses 21 agitation behaviors and The Positive and Negative Syndrome

Scale Excited Component assesses five components of agitation severity (Garriga et al., 2016). Both tools can be utilized for the quick assessment of agitation.

The recommendations from this panel for antipsychotics reflect current psychiatric treatment practices. Haloperidol (first generation antipsychotic) given concurrently with Lorazepam continues to be the mainstream form of treatment for agitation. However, the experts recommend that second generation antipsychotics as the preferred treatment for acute agitation. More specifically, Olanzapine is the most frequently used oral second generation antipsychotic and its efficacy is compared to Haloperidol throughout literature. Risperidone, Aripiprazole, Quetiapine and Asenapine were all found to be effective but there was no consensus recommendation regarding the advantage of one antipsychotic over another (Garriga et al., 2016). The recommendations concluded with a call for further research and the challenges of formulating distinct treatment approaches. The recommendations are intended as a “best management approach” (Garriga et al., 2016).

Several reviews recommended Risperidone (oral and ODT) and Olanzapine (oral) as the first line treatment options for agitation with the second line option being Haloperidol (oral) given concurrently with an oral benzodiazepine (Gault et al., 2012; Vieta et al., 2017; Wilson et al., 2012; Zeller & Rhoades, 2010). The recommended dosages of each medication vary from study to study. A generalized summary of the recommended dosages pertaining to antipsychotics includes: Olanzapine oral 5-10mg, Risperidone oral and ODT 1-3mg, Haloperidol oral 2-10mg (Gault et al., 2012; Vieta et al., 2017; Wilson et al., 2012). For the purpose of this project all three of these antipsychotics will be utilized within the protocol development of this project.

As mentioned previously, the anxiolytic agent most frequently utilized within research studies was Lorazepam. The dosages of oral Lorazepam ranged from 1-2mg and often the studies allowed for repeated dosages until efficacy was established (Gault et al., 2012; Vieta et al., 2017). One review recommended Diazepam oral 5-10mg and Clonazepam oral 1-2mg (Vieta et al., 2017). For the purpose of this project, Lorazepam will be recommended for the treatment of acute anxiety or concurrently with an antipsychotic for the enhanced management of agitation.

Conclusion

Guidelines released by The Occupational Safety and Health Administration provide a structured approach to combatting violence within the workplace. These guidelines promise to mitigate the results of violence for those involved. In an effort to enhance milieu safety within a hospital setting, this review of literature evaluated pharmacological agents and assessment tools in the literature related to the treatment of acute agitation and anxiety. The psychotropic medications to be included in the treatment of agitation/anxiety are: Haloperidol, Olanzapine, Risperidone, and Lorazepam. The psychiatric assessment tools to be included in the nursing education module are the PANSS-EC and CUXOS tool.

METHODS

The purpose of this DNP project was to conduct a quality improvement project using a programmatic review approach along with a review of the literature which was used to develop a nurse education module. The module was developed to improve patient agitation and/or anxiety assessment by psychiatric nursing staff thereby enhancing milieu safety at a large academic medical center in Southern California. The second phase includes implementation of the nurse education module and the addition of a PRN medication protocol. The PRN medications administered by nursing staff will seek to reduce incident rates of verbal / physical / sexual abuse, quantity of code grey alarm activations and use of restrictive measures such as seclusion/restraint. Nursing staff and psychiatric physician residents would be educated on the education module, the recommended psychotropic medications, and lastly the assessment tools. The quality improvement project was evaluated based upon the formation of an EBP toolkit that included a nursing education module and a medication protocol.

Setting and Sample

Phase one of this project, the programmatic review, took place at a large academic medical center located in Southern California which is a Magnet hospital. The inpatient psychiatric nursing unit has three psychiatric units. The two adult units will be the host sites of this quality improvement practice change in phase two. Currently there are approximately thirteen psychiatric physicians employed within the adult psychiatric services. Each adult unit has a primary attending physician that will be closely involved with the project. There are approximately 28 licensed psychiatric technicians and

registered nurses for 1 north (adult psychiatry) and approximately 20 licensed staff members assigned to the 2 south unit (medical psychiatry).

The adult mental health unit known as 1 North has an average census of 18 patients ranging in age from 18 to 64. The adult medical psychiatric unit known as 2 South has an average census of 12 patients ranging in age from 18 to 64 (occasionally an individual 65+ is admitted). The diagnoses of both adult units typically include anxiety disorders, mood disorders, depressive disorders, and psychotic disorders.

Participants

The staff nurses (N=48) of the adult units (1 North and 2 South) will be assigned to mandatory education module on the PRN medications and assessment tools. As this is a programmatic review and proposed practice change project, no completion data was available. However, it is anticipated that based on the support for the project from the administration of the large academic medical center, that this new EBP nursing education module will be assigned to nursing staff. It will be left to the discretion of the facility to assign the implementation of phase two in the future with the DNP candidate available to assist as needed.

Ethical Consideration

This project was approved by the local Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the large academic medical center however, due to time constraints, the project was re-focused as a programmatic review and therefore did not require California State University Los Angeles IRB approval. It is anticipated that the evaluation phase of this project will be completed at the local level since IRB approval was obtained. Further, all recommended psychotropic medications within this protocol are FDA approved

medications for the treatment of agitation and anxiety. The medications recommended are currently available for use in the care of psychiatric patients. This education module that was developed in phase one was not experimental in nature nor was it proposed to determine the efficacy of psychotropic medications. The large academic medical center located in Southern California provided a letter of support (see Appendix D).

Project Design

The goal of this DNP quality improvement project is to translate current evidence-based practice guidelines into patient care practice at a large academic medical center in Southern California. The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Healthcare was used as a framework to guide both phases of this project.

Step One

The issue identified within this project is violence in a psychiatric healthcare setting that is not quickly assessed and treated. This project seeks to implement evidence-based practice in order to support timely de-escalation before an adverse event occurs. The opportunity for improvement will therefore be the incident rates of verbal / physical / sexual abuse, code grey alarms, and restrictive measures (seclusion and restraints).

Step Two

The purpose of this DNP project was to construct a quality improvement project using a programmatic review approach in phase one. This approach included a review of literature that was used to develop a nurse education module that will subsequently improve patient agitation and/or anxiety assessment by psychiatric nursing staff. The improved assessment will enhance milieu safety and facilitate phase two (the implementation plan) at a large academic medical center in Southern California.

Step Three

The stakeholders identified at the large academic medical center in Southern California included administrative staff members in psychiatry, psychiatric physicians (attendings, fellows, residents), and nursing staff personnel.

Step Four

A review of literature was conducted on the topics of violence in the healthcare setting, oral psychotropics utilized to manage acute anxiety and agitation, and lastly assessment tools for evaluating acute anxiety and agitation. The evidence-based guidelines obtained from the review of the literature served as the foundation for the EBP toolkit developed in phase one.

Step Five

The EBP toolkit (nurse education module and PRN medication protocol) was developed and presented to the administrative team at the large academic medical center. The team provided approval and support for phase two of the post-DNP project implementation plan which is as follows: training of nurses and residents across all shifts, assignment of the education module, and lastly completion of pre and post implementation surveys to assess empowerment and confidence.

Step Six

The primary focus of step six is on sustained integration of the evidence-based practice change if it is found to be successful in quality improvement. Recommendations were made at the conclusion of phase one of the project for full, continued implementation of the EBP toolkit (nurse education module and PRN psychotropic protocol) within psychiatry. The recommendations also encouraged future expansion of

this protocol to the adolescent unit with consideration of possible need to utilize different anxiolytic/antipsychotic medications and potentially lower dosages of medications.

Step Seven

The dissemination of results occurred through the presentation of the EBP toolkit to the administrative team which resulted in their approval to proceed with the implementation plan (phase two) as outlined previously.

Instruments

As discussed previously, the Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale Excited Component will be used to screen for agitation (see Appendix E). The Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale Excited Component has been described as “..one of the simplest and most intuitive scales used to assess psychotic agitated patients” (Garriga et al., p.94, 2016). It is recommended for the assessment of agitation in five literature reviews (Garriga et al., 2016; Gault et al., 2012; Vieta et al., 2017; Yu et al., 2017; Zeller & Rhoades, 2010). The tool uses five questions to assess for agitation. Scores of each individual question range from 1 to 7 with overall scores ranging from 5 to 35. Scores of 20 or more are considered severe levels of agitation (Montoya, Valladares, Lizan, San, Escobar, and Paz, 2011). The Crohnbach’s alpha was found to be 0.86 (Montoya, Valladares, Lizan, San, Escobar, and Paz, 2011). These authors were emailed to request permission however the email addresses provided by them were no longer in service or possibly incorrect. An attempt was made to contact the original PANSS authors however two of the authors appear to be deceased and the third author did not have contact information available.

The Clinically Useful Anxiety Outcome Scale (CUXOS) will be used to screen patients for anxiety prior to the administration of an anxiolytic (see Appendix F). Permission was requested and obtained from the author of the tool (see Appendix B). The CUXOS is a 20-item tool that screens anxiety symptomatology and any relevant changes in symptoms (Zimmerman, M., Chelminski, I., Young, D., and Dalrymple, K., 2009). Scores range from 0 to 80 with each question being rated on a scale 0 to 4 in subjective severity. The authors recommend the following scoring range: 0-10 non-anxious, 11-20 minimal, 21-30 mild, 31-44 moderate, 45 and above severe (Zimmerman, M., Chelminski, I., Young, D., and Dalrymple, K., 2009). Staff will be instructed to screen patients with the Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale Excited Component and/or Clinically Useful Anxiety Outcome Scale prior to administering a psychotropic. They will be instructed to reassess the patient again after approximately 30 to 45 minutes in an effort to document improvement of emotion / behavior.

The nurse perception of empowerment will be evaluated through the Conditions for Work Effectiveness Questionnaire (CWEQ) I and II. The Cronbach's alpha reliability was established for individual categories of corresponding questions in the CWEQ I and II (Laschinger, H.K.S., 2012). Questions used from CWEQ I were from the following categories: support, resources, JAS, and ORS. The Cronbach's alpha score for each respective category of the CWEQ I is as follows: 0.88, 0.81, 0.69, 0.89 (Laschinger, H.K.S., 2012). The CWEQ II category of global empowerment was 0.87 (Laschinger, H.K.S., 2012). Permission is granted to use the tool on the authors website.

The Confidence Scale was created by Susan Grundy to evaluate psychomotor skills and confidence of carrying out these skills (Grundy, 1993). It contains five

questions. The questions are rated from 1 to 5 with the interviewee circling the subjective answer that best reflects them. The following numeric responses are linked with their corresponding subjective responses: 1=not at all certain, 2=certain for only a few steps, 3=fairly certain for a good number of steps, 4=certain for almost all steps, and 5=absolutely certain for all steps. Total scores range from 1-5= low confidence and 25=high confidence (Grundy, 1993). Permission was requested from the author to use this tool via email. Author provided permission in her email response (see Appendix B).

Data Collection

The proposed plan for phase two (post-DNP project assessment of the programmatic change) is as follows. First, prior to implementing the protocol, the nurses will be asked to fill out a hard copy survey related to demographic data, perception of empowerment and confidence in administering clinical tools. Survey participation from staff registered nurses and psychiatric technicians will be encouraged through refreshments and pastries provided by the DNP candidate to show gratitude for their voluntary cooperation. The anonymous staff survey will be composed of relevant questions pre-selected from the Conditions for Work Effectiveness Questionnaire (CWEQ) I and II (see Appendix D). Permission was requested from the author (Heather K. Laschlinger) of the questionnaire. A letter of permission will be included in the appendix upon receipt from the author.

The survey will also inquire on demographic data of each individual. The response format will include Likert scales, yes or no responses and select all that apply. The survey will contain approximately 11 questions. The Confidence Scale will contain five additional questions. The empowerment portion of the scale will survey each nurses

perception of support and available resources within their current work environment. The surveys anonymity will be maintained through an assigned code using a random numbers generator which will aid in tracking pre and post survey responses. The hard copy survey results will not have personal identifiers of staff members and will be managed solely by the DNP candidate. Staff will place their completed survey in a plain unmarked envelope to ensure that anonymity is maintained during this process. At this time staff members will be educated on the importance of storing their assigned number in a safe place to ensure that their follow up survey corresponds with their pre-survey assigned tracking number. After completion of the protocol, the survey results will be disposed of in a HIPPA compliant shredding bin at the large academic medical center located in Southern California.

In order to ensure that the project is carried out successfully, the DNP candidate will check in with staff on a weekly basis to monitor progress and assist staff with any questions they may have throughout the project. The Principal Investigator (PI) and the DNP candidate's email and cell phone number will be made available to staff during the projects incorporation. Night shift nurses (2300-0730) are frequently charged with performing nightly audits of patient charts. They will be asked to assist with compliance by auditing each new patients electronic health record to ensure that a PRN medication has been ordered. They will also check to ensure medication consent forms have been signed by the patient and resident. If the patient does not have either one, then the assigned nurse of that patient will be responsible for notifying the day shift nurse to ensure that an order is placed during the day-time and a consent is obtained.

At the conclusion of the project, the surveys will be redistributed and compared with pre-implementation responses. Incident reports of verbal / physical / sexual abuse, code grey alarms, and use of restrictive measures (seclusion/restraints) completed by psychiatric staff members will be reviewed at the conclusion of the three-month time period. Data analysis will be carried out through IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version twenty-four. Microsoft Excel will also be utilized to assist with creating various charts for the results. Run charts and T-tests will be utilized to display potential progress in incident rates and staff perceptions.

RESULTS

Phase one concluded successfully with the approval of stakeholders involved at the large academic medical center. This portion of the project was the most extensive and time consuming. It is likely that phase two which involves implementation of a nurse education module and psychiatric protocol will result in a much shorter time frame in comparison to phase one. Phase two will provide data regarding the efficacy of this proposed quality improvement project. Nurses sense of empowerment will also be reflected at the conclusion of phase two.

Evaluation

The project was a very extensive process and ultimately it was divided into two phases. As the review of literature was underway, there were several articles released about healthcare organizations seeking to make their work environments safer. This internationally pervasive issue has been apparent to healthcare workers for quite some time and it is now being addressed publicly. Workplace safety is the responsibility of congress men and women. They must continue to work diligently to hold healthcare organizations accountable for the safety of medical and ancillary staff. The literature and current legislative efforts support the relevance of this topic as well as the urgency.

DISCUSSION

The project had an unexpected change in its course, as a result the focus was changed from a quality improvement project that involved implementation to a quality improvement project that involved a programmatic evaluation and literature review to provide evidence-based practice recommendations to address identified gaps in the program. Significant information was identified from the performance and completion of phase one of this project. First, the topic was relevant on a national level and at the local level which was the designated project site of this quality improvement project. Second, the literature review identified various options for psychotropics and assessment tools. The medications and assessment tools selected for phase two of this project were also aligned with the identified needs of the units. For example, some assessment tools were too extensive and therefore not appropriate for acute agitation / anxiety on an inpatient unit. Additionally, some oral psychotropics were found to be effective treatment options but the onset of action was not as quick as those selected for this project.

After reviewing the program level data provided by psychiatric administrative staff at the large academic medical center, it was apparent that workplace violence was on the rise on the acute adult unit in 2019 but slightly decreased on the medical-psychiatric unit in 2019 (from 2018 data comparison). Battery reports increased on the acute adult psychiatric unit but decreased drastically on the medical psychiatric unit in 2019. Lastly, code grey alarms increased on the medical psychiatric unit and decreased on the acute adult psychiatric unit. Interpretation of data is difficult to accurately analyze. The acute adult psychiatric unit has patients that are typically high in psychiatric acuity when compared to the medical-psychiatric unit. Therefore, patients on the acute

psychiatric unit may be escalating to aggression quicker than those on the medical-psychiatric unit and this could potentially explain the higher number of workplace violence and battery reports in 2019.

Thus far 2020 has demonstrated one workplace violence event on the medical psychiatric unit according to data obtained March 10, 2020. Additionally, there have been ten incidents of workplace violence on the acute adult psychiatric unit. There have been twelve code grey alarm activations on the acute adult psychiatric unit and activation on the adult medical-psychiatric unit in 2020 (per March 10, 2020 data). This data demonstrates ongoing violence within the workplace setting. It should be noted that despite exclusion of the adolescent psychiatric unit within this project, the program level data supports high numbers of code grey alarm activations that is almost on par with the acute adult psychiatric unit and therefore it would potentially benefit from adoption once project results from the adult units have been reviewed.

Limitations

The most significant challenge at the onset of this project was in the definition of the topic itself. There are some healthcare leaders that feel workplace violence does not apply to psychiatry as the patient's mental status upon admission prevents them from being held liable for assault. This limitation was addressed as it was clarified that any patient who abuses a staff member is subject to a police report and then prosecution is subsequently left up to the district attorney. Staff are advised of their right to press charges against any individual (patient or visitor) that has assaulted them. Therefore, the limitation of the workplace violence topic as it applies to inpatient psychiatry was

mitigated for this project through support of the current policies in place at this large academic medical center.

The next significant limitation that occurred during this project was the challenge of defining the population of focus for this quality improvement project. Specifically, the psychiatric patient population is classified by the IRB as a vulnerable population. As such, certain additional protections must be put into place to ensure that the study not only qualifies for exempt status, but also that it protects any and all of the rights that the psychiatric patient has as part of their routine care. This limitation was mitigated by switching the focus of quality improvement data collection and results review from the psychiatric patient to the psychiatric nurse. Targeting the nursing education module that originated from the programmatic review as well as the future desired practice changes, allowed the student to demonstrate to the academic medical center administrative team and the local IRB, the value of the project in addressing workplace violence through the development of the evidence-based toolkit (the nursing education module and the PRN medication protocol).

The third limitation encountered during this DNP project was in the implementation of phase two at the proposed institution. Due to the time requirements to address all of the challenges encountered in phase one, the implementation of phase two was projected to occur on April 1, 2020. As of that date in the timeline, there were institutional precautions in place that prevented the execution of this plan. These precautions were the result of a world-wide viral pandemic that not only impacted the institution but also the community as a whole. The coronavirus pandemic created a need for social distancing in order to preserve the health of individuals worldwide. Restrictive

measures were aimed at social events, various occupations, specialized healthcare fields and various other pertinent aspects of living.

These restrictions not only indefinitely prevented the implementation of phase two but they also changed the way healthcare workers cared for patients. For example, the implementation of telehealth in the acute care setting. While inpatient psychiatry did not transition entirely to telehealth rounding, there are some physicians who opted to trial patient care assessments through this new mode of technology. As a result, the operational aspects of phase two of this project would have to have been altered requiring additional time, resources, etc. Finally, the changes occurring in healthcare during this time, the DNP project deadline, and the health of staff members, all played a substantial role in the inability to implement phase two.

The remaining phase two limitations are projected limitations. First, the resident physicians on-call are no longer on-site during the night shift due to policy changes last year. Thus, they may not be available to sign consent forms and order PRN psychotropics within one hour of a patient's arrival to the inpatient psychiatric unit. This limitation could be addressed by requesting that the day shift resident order a PRN psychotropic medication and sign subsequent medication consent forms with the patient during their assessment in the emergency department or medical unit prior to the patient's overnight arrival.

The second projected limitation is in the varying level of physician comfort in regards to benzodiazepine prescription. The research supports the use of oral lorazepam for acute anxiety treatment however some physicians fear dependence and medication seeking behaviors so they may be reluctant to prescribe this medication. To address this

limitation, stakeholders were advised of the recommended medications and no one raised objections however if those opinions should change, they could utilize alternative non-benzodiazepine psychotropic options. Use of alternative psychotropics for the treatment of acute anxiety would be done with the foreknowledge that those PRN's may not be as effective at treating anxiety as the recommended lorazepam.

Lastly, the nurse adoption of new changes could have potentially been a future limitation of this project. Nurses accustomed to assessing patients may be reluctant to incorporate new changes and deem them as being "too timely". This limitation would have been addressed through encouragement and transparency related to the long-term goal. It is likely that nurses will adopt the changes in practice if they know the changes are intended to enhance their overall safety and potentially improve their sense of empowerment. These preliminary projections are not intended to be exhaustive of all potential limitations and there may have been additional limitations discovered if phase two had been implemented.

CONCLUSION

This DNP project sought to conduct a quality improvement project using a programmatic review approach along with a review of the literature to develop a nurse education module in order to improve patient agitation and/or anxiety assessment. The response of psychiatric nursing staff would have been enhanced through the utilization of a PRN medication protocol and subsequently milieu safety would have improved at a large academic medical center in Southern California. Due to time limitations, the project was divided into two phases. The first phase of this DNP project was completed. Phase one consisted of a programmatic review with administrative stakeholders at the academic medical center that included a gap analysis of current and needed evidence-based activities, in the form of a toolkit, that could help reduce workplace violence. This toolkit also included an extensive review of the literature for the purposes of: 1) development of a nurse education module to help nurses understand the importance of earlier intervention to prevent crisis or de-escalate crisis and 2) development of a “PRN” medication protocol. Both of these toolkit options will be strongly encouraged for nursing administrators at the academic medical center. Three significant limitations led to the need to split the project into two phases. First, there was healthcare leader disagreement concerning the definition of workplace violence in relation to the psychiatric patient. This issue was addressed, however the investigation into defining the concept led to a significant time delay. Secondly, there was a challenge in defining the population of focus (psychiatric patients versus psychiatric nurses) for this quality improvement project. Although the program will measure aggregate patient information, the focus was developed around the need to improve nursing assessment in order to reduce the number

of times patients will experience a crisis that would otherwise result in a violent outcome. Thirdly, the project timeline was nearing expiration and a viral pandemic created new requirements for various protective measures for patients and staff members which prevented the implementation of phase two. Reducing workplace violence through evidence-based practice change represents a significant opportunity to improve both the quality of life for patients and the staff who care for them before, during and after their psychiatric crisis.

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APPENDIX A

DSM V DIAGNOSES ASSOCIATED WITH AGGRESSION

Table 2

DSM V Diagnosis	Physical/sexual aggression or violence towards others as diagnostic criteria YES / NO	Special Consideration	Statistics
Psychotic disorders			
Schizophrenia	NO; see special consideration for associated features	“Aggression is more frequent for younger males and for individuals with a past history of violence, non-adherence with treatment, substance abuse and impulsivity. It should be noted that the vast majority of persons with schizophrenia are not aggressive and are more frequently victimized than are individuals in the general population” (p.101).	Adults in United States with schizophrenia diagnosis approximate 1.1% of population (NAMI, 2019)
Schizoaffective Disorder	NO		
Unspecified Schizophrenia Spectrum and Other Psychotic Disorder	NO		
Mood disorders			
Bipolar I Disorder	See special consideration	“Mood disturbance” of manic episode <u>may</u> require “hospitalization to prevent harm to self or others” (p.124).	Adults in United States with schizophrenia diagnosis approximate 1.1% of population (NAMI, 2019). No specification of type I or II.
Bipolar II Disorder	NO		
Cyclothymic Disorder	NO		
Unspecified Bipolar and Related Disorder	NO		

Depressive Disorders				
Major Depressive Disorder	NO		Adults in United States with depressive disorder diagnosis/episode approximate 6.9% of population (NAMI, 2019)	
Persistent Depressive Disorder	NO			
Unspecified Depressive Disorder	NO			
Anxiety disorders				
Social Anxiety Disorder	NO			
Panic Disorder	NO			
Generalized Anxiety Disorder	NO			
Unspecified Anxiety Disorder	NO			
Substance abuse disorders				
Alcohol Use Disorder	NO		Adults in United States with substance use disorder diagnosis approximate 20.2 million individuals within the population (NAMI, 2019). No specification of substance use disorder.	
Alcohol Intoxication	YES	Potential for “inappropriate sexual or aggressive behavior” (p.497)		
Alcohol Withdrawal	NO			
Cannabis Use Disorder	NO			
Cannabis Intoxication	NO			
Cannabis Withdrawal	YES	Potential for “aggression” (p.518)		
Sedative, Hypnotic or Anxiolytic Use Disorder	YES	Potential for “physical fights” (p.550)		
Sedative, Hypnotic or Anxiolytic Intoxication	YES	Potential for “inappropriate sexual or aggressive behavior” (p.556)		
Sedative, Hypnotic or Anxiolytic Withdrawal	NO			
Stimulant Use Disorder	NO			
Stimulant Intoxication	NO			
Stimulant Withdrawal	NO			
Trauma and Stressor Related Disorders				
Posttraumatic Stress Disorder	YES	“..Verbal or physical aggression toward people or		

		objects” may potentially be present (p.272).
Acute Stress Disorder	YES	“..Verbal or physical aggression toward people or objects” may potentially be present (p.281).
Adjustment Disorders	NO	
Unspecified Trauma and Stressor Related Disorder	NO	
Personality Disorders		
Paranoid Personality Disorder	NO	
Schizoid Personality Disorder	NO	
Schizotypal Personality Disorder	NO	
Antisocial Personality Disorder	YES	“..Repeated physical fights or assaults” (p.659)
Borderline Personality Disorder	YES	Potential for “..recurrent physical fights” (p.663)
Histrionic Personality Disorder	NO	
Narcissistic Personality Disorder	NO	
Avoidant Personality Disorder	NO	
Dependent Personality Disorder	NO	
Obsessive-Compulsive Personality Disorder	NO	
Disruptive, Impulse-Control and Conduct Disorders		
Oppositional Defiant Disorder	NO	Typical onset in pediatric / adolescent population. Rare onset in adults (p.461).
Conduct Disorder	YES	“Aggression to people and animals” (p.469). Typical onset in pediatric / adolescent population. Rare onset in adults (p.461). Aggression is consequence of “poorly controlled emotion” (p.461)
Intermittent Explosive Disorder	YES	“Verbal aggression...or physical aggression toward property, animals or other individuals..” (p.466). Result

		of “poorly controlled emotion” (p.461)
Unspecified Disruptive, Impulse- Control and Conduct Disorder	NO	
Neurodevelopmental Disorders		
Autism Spectrum Disorder	NO	Symptomatology typically presents in childhood (p.53)
Attention- Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder	NO	Age of onset is childhood (p.61)

Note. American Psychiatric Association, 2013

APPENDIX B

PERMISSION LETTERS

11/18/19
Neuropsychiatry

To whom it may concern:

UCI Neuropsychiatry has granted Rachel Medina permission to conduct a DNP quality improvement project at UCIMC on 1N and 2S adult inpatient psychiatric units. Since the project will include a PRN medication protocol ordered on all newly admitted psychiatric patients, attending physician approval and guidance will be required. As presented, the project will involve the psychiatric medical residents, with the intent to order the medication(s) within 1 hour of admission and the registered nurses, for assessment of need as well as efficacy of the medication for each patient that requires a PRN. The director or nurse manager or designee, in order to maintain exempt status and provide the DNP candidate with de-identified data, will conduct data collection. All IR reports and any project related data is to be de-identified prior to review by the DNP student to comply with IRB exempt standards.

Sincerely,

Susanlee Wisotzkey
Director
Neuropsychiatry

CUXOS scale

3 messages

Rachel Medina <rmedina18@csu.fullerton.edu> Sat, Oct 19, 2019 at 1:00 PM
To: [REDACTED]

Good afternoon Mark, I am emailing you to request use of the CUXOS scale for my upcoming DNP project. I would like to use it in its entirety or in a modified format (if needed). If a formal request process is required please advise me how to proceed with that process. Thank you kindly for your time and I look forward to hearing back from you.

Rachel Medina

Zimmerman, Mark MD <[REDACTED]> Sat, Oct 19, 2019 at 2:10 PM
To: Rachel Medina <rmedina18@csu.fullerton.edu>

You have my permission to use the measure in your study. You can access it at www.outcometracker.org

-----Original Message-----

From: Rachel Medina <rmedina18@csu.fullerton.edu>
Sent: Saturday, October 19, 2019 4:00 PM
To: Zimmerman, Mark MD <[REDACTED]>
Subject: CUXOS scale

WARNING: This email originated outside of Lifespan and our authorized business partners. USE CAUTION when clicking on links or attachments.

Good afternoon Mark, I am emailing you to request use of the CUXOS scale for my upcoming DNP project. I would like to use it in its entirety or in a modified format (if needed). If a formal request process is required please advise me how to proceed with that process. Thank you kindly for your time and I look forward to hearing back from you.

Rachel Medina

This transmission is intended only for the addressee(s) listed above and may contain information that is confidential. If you are not the addressee, any use, disclosure, copying or communication of the contents of this message is prohibited. Please contact me if this message was transmitted in error.

Permission to Use The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics <noreply@qualtrics-survey.com>
to me

Mon, Jun 17, 2019,
10:31 AM

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Citation: Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(3), 175-182. doi:10.1111/wvn.12223

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Please contact UIHCNursingResearchandEBP@uiowa.edu or 319-384-9098 with questions.

Permission to use C-Scale - Rachel Medina - Request more information

Grundy, Susan <[REDACTED]>

Sun, Oct 20, 2019,
9:55 PM

to me

Hello Rachel:

I would be delighted to send you the permission you need to use the C-Scale and an electronic version of the C-Scale to use as a template for your study. In the permission statement I usually include the title of the study or a working title and the institution where you are earning your DNP.

Sincerely,

Susan Grundy, Ed.D., M.S.N., R.N.
Professor Emeritus Nursing
California State University

APPENDIX C**NURSE PERCEPTION OF EMPOWERMENT SURVEY**Demographic Data**Age:**

21-30

31-40

41-50

51-60

61-70

Gender:

Male

Female

Years of experience:

0-1

1-5

6-10

10-20

20-30

35+

Number of years working at this academic hospital:

0-1

1-5

6-10

10-20

20-30

35+

Number of years working in psychiatry:

0-1

1-5

6-10

10-20

20-30

35+

Which shift do you work?

AM

PM

NOC

Nurse Empowerment

Score each question below from 1-5 based upon the following numeric descriptions: 1= none, 3= some, 5= a lot. Questions derived from Conditions for Work

Effectiveness Questionnaire I and II (Laschinger, H.K.S., & Shamian, J., 1994;

Laschinger, H.K.S., Finegan, J., Shamian, J., & Wilk, P., 2001)

1. How much access to support do you have in your present job?
 - Help when there is a work crisis 1 / 2 / 3/ 4 / 5
 - Help in getting materials and supplies needed to get the job done 1 / 2 / 3/ 4 / 5

2. How much access to resources do you have in your present job?
 - Having supplies necessary for the job? 1 / 2 / 3/ 4 / 5
 - Acquiring temporary help when needed? 1 / 2 / 3/ 4 / 5
 - Influencing decisions about obtaining supplies for your unit? 1 / 2 / 3/ 4 / 5

3. In my work setting / job:
 - The number of approvals needed for nonroutine decisions are 1 / 2 / 3/ 4 / 5

4. How much opportunity do you have for these activities in your present job:
 - Collaborating on patient care with physicians 1 / 2 / 3/ 4 / 5
 - Receiving helpful feedback from physicians 1 / 2 / 3/ 4 / 5
 - Having physicians ask for your opinion 1 / 2 / 3/ 4 / 5

5. How much of each kind of opportunity do you have in your present job? 1 / 2 / 3/ 4 / 5
 - Overall, my current work environment empowers me to accomplish my work in an effective manner 1 / 2 / 3/ 4 / 5
 - Overall, I consider my workplace to be an empowering environment 1 / 2 / 3/ 4 / 5

APPENDIX D**CONFIDENCE SCALE (C-SCALE)**

Score each question below from 1-5 based upon the following numeric descriptions: 1=not at all certain, 2=certain for only a few steps, 3=fairly certain for a good number of steps, 4=certain for almost all steps, 5=absolutely certain for all steps. Scoring ranges: 1-5 = low confidence, 25 = high confidence (Grundy, S., 1993)

- 1) I am certain that my performance is correct
- 2) I feel that I perform the task without hesitation
- 3) My performance would convince the observer that I'm competent
- 4) I feel sure of myself as I perform the task
- 5) I feel satisfied with my performance

APPENDIX E**POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE SYNDROME SCALE – EXCITED COMPONENT
(PANSS-EC)**

Score each question below from 1-7 based upon the following numeric descriptions:

1=not present, 2=minimal, 3=mild, 4=moderate, 5=moderate-severe, 6=severe,
7=extremely severe (Montoya, A., Valladares, A., Lizan, L., San, L., Escobar, R., and
Paz, S., 2011)

1. Poor impulse control
2. Tension
3. Hostility
4. Lack of cooperation
5. Excitement

APPENDIX F**CLINICALLY USEFUL ANXIETY OUTCOME SCALE (CUXOS)**

Score each question below from 0-4 based upon the following numeric descriptions:

0=Not at all true, 1=rarely true, 2=sometimes true, 3=often true, 4=almost always true.

Authors recommend the following anxiety scores: 0-10 non-anxious, 11-20 minimal, 21-30 mild, 31-44 moderate, 45 and above severe (Zimmerman, M., Chelminski, I., Young,

D., and Dalrymple, K., 2009)

During the past week, including today:

1. I felt nervous or anxious
2. I worried a lot that something bad might happen
3. I worried too much about things
4. I was jumpy and easily startled by noises
5. I felt “keyed up” or “on edge”
6. I felt scared
7. I had muscle tension or muscle aches
8. I felt jittery
9. I was short of breath
10. My heart was pounding or racing
11. I had cold, clammy hands
12. I had a dry mouth
13. I was dizzy or lightheaded
14. I felt sick to my stomach (nauseated)

15. I had diarrhea
16. I had hot flashes or chills
17. I urinated frequently
18. I felt a lump in my throat
19. I was sweating
20. I had tingling feelings in my fingers or feet